

Multimedia Appendix 1.

TeleHealthIndex-O Organizational Self-Assessment Questionnaire (Version 1.0)

“This questionnaire is administered as part of the assessment of the maturity of telemedicine services within a healthcare organization using the TeleHealthIndex-O methodology.

The purpose of the survey is to assess the current level of implementation and maturity of telemedicine services, including the use of artificial intelligence technologies, as well as the development of digital infrastructure and managerial processes within the healthcare organization.

The questionnaire is designed to support a comprehensive organizational self-assessment, enabling the identification of strengths and areas requiring further development for internal analysis, strategic planning, and the subsequent improvement of telemedicine services and digital health transformation processes.

Please answer the questions based on the actual state of affairs in your organization.

The questionnaire is intended exclusively for voluntary internal organizational self-assessment and does not constitute an instrument for external audit, control, regulatory inspection, accreditation, or ranking of healthcare organizations. Completion of the questionnaire does not imply automatic transmission of data to governmental authorities or any other external entities.

Each item is assessed using an ordinal scoring scale ranging from 0 to 5, where the values represent levels of operational maturity of the corresponding processes (0 — the process is absent; 5 — a high level of integration and maturity has been achieved).

Survey results are used exclusively in aggregated form and do not include the identification of individual persons, organizational units, or any personal data.

Informed Consent of the Respondent

This survey is conducted as part of the voluntary participation of a healthcare organization in the assessment of the digital maturity of telemedicine services. Participation of individual respondents (including department heads, healthcare professionals, and IT staff representatives) is voluntary.

I confirm that I:

- have been informed about the purpose and procedures of the survey;
- understand that the results will be used exclusively in an aggregated, analytical, and scientific form;
- acknowledge that the survey is not intended as a tool for monitoring or evaluating individual professional performance;
- understand that I may withdraw from the survey at any stage without providing any explanation.

Yes, I agree to participate in the survey

No, I do not agree to participate in the survey

Instruction:

For each indicator, please select one level (0–5) that most accurately reflects the current level of development of telemedicine services in your organization.

1. Use of Telemedicine

1.1 Scope of Telemedicine Implementation

Over the past 12 months, telemedicine consultations (physician-to-physician and physician-to-patient) have been actively used within the organization.

Please assess the level using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Telemedicine is not used	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Isolated pilot implementations have been conducted (less than 10% of physicians involved)	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Partial implementation (up to 50% of physicians involved)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Regular use across the majority of departments	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Wide-scale implementation (approximately 75–90% of staff involved)	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Full integration into routine clinical processes	<input type="checkbox"/>

1.2 Recording and Reporting of Telemedicine Services

A system for the registration and analysis of telemedicine consultations is in place within the organization.

Please assess the level of development of recording and analytical processes using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No recording of telemedicine services is in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Recording is performed manually and on an irregular basis	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Individual cases are recorded without systematic data aggregation or analysis	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Regular recording is conducted within the medical information system (MIS), but without analytical processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Automated recording with regular reporting is implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Full integration with the National Telemedicine Network (NTN) with automated performance analysis	<input type="checkbox"/>

1.3 Interregional Collaboration

The organization uses telemedicine technologies for interregional collaboration with other healthcare organizations.

Please assess the level of collaboration using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No interregional collaboration is in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Isolated telemedicine consultations with other regions are conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Interregional collaboration is irregular and not supported by a shared digital platform	<input type="checkbox"/>

3	Regular interregional telemedicine consultations are conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Partial or full integration with the National Telemedicine Network (NTN) and/or regional medical information systems has been implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Full interregional collaboration with automated exchange of medical data is ensured	<input type="checkbox"/>

1.4 Telemonitoring and Mobile Applications

The organization uses clinical telemonitoring solutions and mobile health (mHealth) applications for the remote monitoring and support of patients.

Please assess the level of implementation and use using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Telemonitoring solutions and mobile applications are not used	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Pilot projects are implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Telemonitoring and mHealth applications are applied in selected clinical conditions (specific disease areas)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Regular use is established for selected patient groups	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Solutions are integrated with the medical information system (MIS), with regular data exchange ensured	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Systematic use with automated data transmission and advanced analytics, including elements of artificial intelligence	<input type="checkbox"/>

1.5 Internal Quality Assessment and Analytics

The organization operates an internal quality assurance and data-driven analytics system for assessing the effectiveness of telemedicine services.

Please assess the level of development of this system using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No quality control or analytics is conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Ad hoc quality checks are performed without an approved methodology	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Manual analysis is conducted without the use of key performance indicators (KPIs)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Regular assessment is implemented with elements of automation	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	A system of key performance indicators (KPIs) with automated reporting is in use	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A comprehensive quality assurance system with data visualization and predictive analytics is operational (within the MIS or a business intelligence platform)	<input type="checkbox"/>

2. Application of Artificial Intelligence Technologies

2.1 Use of Artificial Intelligence in Clinical and Diagnostic Tasks

The organization uses artificial intelligence (AI) technologies to support clinical decision-making, diagnostics, and patient monitoring.

Please assess the level of implementation using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are not used	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Individual AI functions are being tested without clinical application	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	AI is used irregularly (e.g., for image analysis without system integration)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Local AI solutions are implemented in several clinical areas but are not integrated with the medical information system (MIS)	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	AI is integrated into clinical workflows and supports physician decision-making	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	AI systematically supports clinical decision-making, predictive analytics, and real-time patient monitoring	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.2 Use of Artificial Intelligence in Administrative Telemedicine Processes

The organization uses artificial intelligence (AI) technologies to optimize administrative and operational telemedicine processes, including consultation scheduling, automated reporting, electronic document management, and resource management.

Please assess the level of implementation using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Artificial intelligence (AI) is not used in telemedicine operational processes	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Individual AI functions are being tested (e.g., automated consultation scheduling)	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Separate AI modules are applied for reporting or document processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	AI is regularly used for several telemedicine-related administrative tasks	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	AI solutions are integrated with the medical information system (MIS) and the National Telemedicine Network (NTN) platforms	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	AI systematically supports scheduling, reporting, and resource management of telemedicine services, including workload forecasting and real-time process optimization	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.3 Documentation and Governance of Artificial Intelligence Use

The organization has developed and maintains documentation governing the implementation and use of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies.
Please assess the level of systematization using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No documentation governing the use of artificial intelligence is in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Individual records or reports related to pilot AI projects are maintained	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Basic documentation exists, but without formally approved regulations or procedures	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Internal guidelines for the use of AI have been developed, but are not regularly updated	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	An approved regulatory framework is in place, with regular updates and audits conducted by designated responsible personnel	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A comprehensive governance system has been established, including an ethical AI use policy, risk assessment procedures, and organization-level reporting	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.4 Evaluation of Artificial Intelligence System Performance

The organization conducts data-driven evaluations of the effectiveness and accuracy of artificial intelligence (AI) systems.

Please assess the level of systematization and regularity of such evaluations using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No evaluation of AI system effectiveness or accuracy is conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Isolated assessments are performed without an approved methodology	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Individual AI systems are evaluated, but without regularity or standardization	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	AI accuracy is periodically assessed, for example through expert review and comparison with physician-generated results	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	An approved evaluation methodology is in place, using quantitative performance metrics (e.g., accuracy, sensitivity, specificity)	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A comprehensive AI performance monitoring system is implemented, including automated data collection, validation, reporting, and model refinement based on evaluation results	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.5 External Collaboration and Participation in Artificial Intelligence Projects in Telemedicine

The organization collaborates with external partners (such as national centers, startups, and research institutions) and participates in projects aimed at the development of artificial intelligence and digital technologies in telemedicine.

Please assess the level of activity and engagement using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No external collaboration or participation in AI-related projects is in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Isolated contacts have been established, or an intention to collaborate has been expressed	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Participation is limited to individual events or consultations	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	The organization has participated in one or more pilot AI projects	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Regular collaboration has been established with external AI platforms, startups, or research centers, including data exchange for solution testing	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	The organization is an active participant in national or international initiatives and a partner in the implementation of AI technologies in healthcare	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Level of Staff Preparedness and Training

3.1 Staff Training in Digital Technologies

The organization provides training for staff (physicians, nursing, and administrative personnel) in digital technologies and telemedicine.

Please assess the proportion of staff who have completed such training using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No staff training in digital technologies or telemedicine is conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Up to 25% of staff have completed relevant training	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	26–50% of staff have completed relevant training	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	51–75% of staff have completed relevant training	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	76–90% of staff have completed relevant training	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	More than 90% of staff have completed training and regularly update their competencies through approved programs or external educational platforms in digital health	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.2 Availability and Role of Digital Coordinators

Digital coordinators (mentors) are appointed within the organization's departments to support the implementation of digital tools, provide staff training, and facilitate interaction with the IT department.

Please assess the level of organization of digital coordination using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No digital coordinators are in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Responsible individuals are identified informally	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Digital coordinators are appointed, but their role is limited to consultative support	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Digital coordinators actively participate in the implementation of digital solutions	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Digital coordination is embedded within departmental structures and supported by organizational leadership	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A sustainable system of digital mentors is in place, supported by approved internal training standards and regular reporting	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.3 Use of Online Learning Platforms for Staff Training

The organization provides access to online courses and educational platforms (e.g., Coursera, Stepik, Platonus, OpenEdu, etc.) that are used to develop digital competencies among staff members.

Please assess the level of access and engagement using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No access to online learning platforms is available	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Access is available, but use is rare or limited to individual initiatives	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Staff independently complete individual courses without organizational coordination	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Online learning is used at the initiative of the organization (e.g., recommended courses)	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Online learning platforms are integrated into the formal continuing professional development system	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Online learning is systematically embedded in the digital workforce development plan, supports individualized learning pathways, and training outcomes are assessed and considered in staff appraisal or certification	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.4 Updating and Revision of Training Programs

The organization conducts regular updates and reviews of training programs and courses in digital technologies, telemedicine, and artificial intelligence.

Please assess the level of systematization and frequency of updates using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Training programs have not been updated for more than two years	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Programs have been updated once, without a systematic approach	<input type="checkbox"/>

2	Updates are performed irregularly, at the initiative of individual departments	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Programs are reviewed in response to changes in regulatory or normative documents	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	An approved update cycle is in place (at least once every two years)	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A continuous improvement system is implemented, with ongoing content updates based on feedback, competency analysis, and evaluation of training effectiveness	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.5 Collaboration with Universities and Training Partners

The organization collaborates with universities, competence centers, and other partners in the fields of digital education and telemedicine.

Please assess the level of partnership using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No formal agreements or partnerships are in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	One partnership agreement has been signed, without practical implementation	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Partnerships are implemented on an ad hoc basis (e.g., participation in individual courses or events)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Active collaboration is established with one university or training partner, including joint training programs	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Active collaboration with multiple organizations is in place, including regular courses and exchange of specialists	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A sustainable partnership network with universities and IT companies has been established; joint programs are embedded in the staff development strategy, and digital internships and structured knowledge exchange are implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>

4. Infrastructure and Technical Capacity

4.1 Network Infrastructure and Internet Connectivity for Telemedicine

The organization has network infrastructure and reliable internet connectivity that support telemedicine services and the transmission of medical data.

Please assess the quality and availability of internet connectivity using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Stable internet connectivity is not available	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Connectivity is unstable, and bandwidth is insufficient for video consultations	<input type="checkbox"/>

2	Stable connectivity is available, but not across all departments	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Reliable internet access is ensured in core departments	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	High-speed connectivity is available across all departments, supporting HD-quality video communication	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Full digital network integration is achieved, including redundant connectivity channels to ensure uninterrupted operation of telemedicine services	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.2 Telemedicine Equipment and Dedicated Workspaces

The organization has established and equipped dedicated workspaces for conducting telemedicine consultations and videoconferencing (physician-to-physician and physician-to-patient).

The assessment includes stationary and mobile workstations, the quality of audio and video communication, and the availability of medical peripheral devices (such as digital stethoscopes, ECG devices, high-resolution cameras, and other related equipment).

Please assess the level of equipment and readiness using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Telemedicine equipment and dedicated workspaces are not available	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Only basic devices are available (e.g., computers without video capabilities or not intended for telemedicine consultations)	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	A single dedicated room is equipped for telemedicine consultations	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Multiple areas are equipped with video systems and basic medical peripheral devices	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Infrastructure meets telemedicine room standards, including specialized cameras, audio systems, and medical peripheral devices	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Optimized infrastructure is in place, including integration of stationary and mobile solutions, the ability to connect from any department, backup equipment, and remote monitoring of technical reliability	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.3 Technical Data Protection and Cybersecurity

The organization ensures technical protection of personal medical data and has implemented cybersecurity measures.

Please assess the level of data protection and cybersecurity using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No technical data protection measures are in place	<input type="checkbox"/>

1	Only basic antivirus solutions are used, without data encryption	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Secure data transmission channels are partially implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	VPN/SSL technologies are used for data transmission	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Certified information security solutions have been implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	The system fully complies with GOST and/or ISO standards, with continuous information security auditing, monitoring, and formal reporting to designated responsible personnel	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.4 Technical Support and IT Infrastructure Monitoring

The organization has an established technical support and IT infrastructure monitoring system to ensure the operation of telemedicine services.

The assessment includes the availability of an IT department or designated specialists, network and server monitoring systems, as well as backup power supply and failure recovery mechanisms.

Please assess the level of organization using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No IT support service is in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Technical support is provided irregularly and without formalized procedures	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	A designated specialist is available, but monitoring is performed manually	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	An IT department is operational, providing basic monitoring of network and equipment status	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Automated infrastructure monitoring and backup power supply systems are implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Round-the-clock (24/7) technical support is provided, with automated incident alerts, real-time failure analytics, and an established Business Continuity Plan (BCP)	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.5 Modern Solutions and Infrastructure Upgrades

The organization actively implements modern technological solutions and performs regular updates of the IT infrastructure supporting telemedicine services.

The assessment takes into account equipment replacement, migration to cloud or hybrid platforms, the use of mobile stations, backup storage systems, and integration with the National Telemedicine Network (NTN).

Please assess the level of infrastructure modernization using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Infrastructure has not been upgraded for more than three years	<input type="checkbox"/>

1	Individual components (e.g., computers, peripheral devices) have been updated without improving the overall system architecture	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Partial upgrades have been implemented, but without integration with telemedicine platforms	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Modern solutions (e.g., cloud services, mobile stations) have been implemented to provide basic operational flexibility	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	A comprehensive infrastructure upgrade has been completed within the past three years, including network and server components	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A scalable hybrid infrastructure is in place, featuring cloud services, automated backup systems, integration with the National Telemedicine Network (NTN), and support for automated system updates	<input type="checkbox"/>

5. Regulatory Framework and Protocols

5.1 Availability of an Internal Regulatory Framework for Telemedicine

The organization has developed and maintains an internal regulatory framework governing telemedicine activities.

Please assess the availability and completeness of relevant documents using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No internal regulatory documents are in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Individual internal orders or directives exist, but without a unified structure	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Internal policies or regulations have been developed but have not been formally approved	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Core documents have been formally approved (e.g., orders, policies, instructions)	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	A comprehensive set of regulatory documents has been established, including regulations and patient care or service routing protocols	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	The regulatory framework is fully implemented and regularly updated in accordance with national requirements and international guidelines	<input type="checkbox"/>

5.2 Definition and Regulation of Staff Roles and Responsibilities

The organization has defined and formally regulated roles and responsibilities of staff involved in telemedicine processes, including physicians, IT specialists, and administrative personnel.

Please assess the level of formalization using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Roles and responsibilities are not defined	<input type="checkbox"/>

1	Responsibilities are defined informally	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Roles are documented only within individual departments	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Job descriptions including elements of digital and telemedicine-related functions have been formally approved	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Formal regulations defining the distribution of responsibilities across departments and services have been developed	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	The system of roles and responsibilities is integrated into the organization's human resources and IT policies and is considered in staff performance evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>

5.3 Regulatory Framework and Ethical Standards for Data Protection

The organization has an approved and operational internal regulatory framework governing confidentiality, personal data protection, informed consent, and digital ethics. Please assess the level of regulatory and ethical framework implementation using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No relevant regulatory or ethical documents are in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Individual orders or instructions exist, but without a systematic framework	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Data protection policies are in place but are not regularly updated	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Local regulatory documents have been developed and are being applied in practice	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	The regulatory framework is regularly updated, and internal audits are conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	All processes are fully regulated, comprehensive regulatory and ethical support for digital activities is ensured, staff training is provided, and compliance with standards is systematically monitored	<input type="checkbox"/>

5.4 Compliance Monitoring and Regulatory Audit

The organization has an internal system for monitoring and auditing compliance with regulatory requirements related to telemedicine activities. Please assess the level of organization of compliance control using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No compliance monitoring or audit is conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Compliance checks are conducted on an ad hoc basis	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	A compliance committee has been established, but without regular audits	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Regulatory reviews are conducted annually	<input type="checkbox"/>

4	An internal audit system for digital and telemedicine-related processes is in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Continuous compliance monitoring is implemented, with automated reporting and integration into the organization's quality management system	<input type="checkbox"/>

5.5 Updating and Revision of Regulatory Documents

The organization systematically reviews and updates internal regulatory documents in accordance with changes in legislation and technologies.

Please assess the level of systematization using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No updates have been performed	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Updates were last implemented more than two years ago	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Updates are carried out irregularly	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Updates are performed in response to the introduction of new regulatory or legal requirements	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	A scheduled review cycle is established (every 1–2 years)	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A continuous updating system is in place, incorporating stakeholder feedback, integration with external regulatory frameworks, and formal documentation of updates in an official registry	<input type="checkbox"/>

6. Governance and Coordination

6.1 Leadership and Accountability for Digital Transformation

The organization has an established digital project governance structure, with clearly defined responsibilities and effective coordination of digital transformation initiatives.

Please assess the level of governance using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No individuals responsible for digital transformation are designated	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	A single responsible individual is appointed, without formal managerial authority	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Digital coordinators are designated within individual departments	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	A cross-functional digital transformation working group or committee is in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	A dedicated digital transformation leader is appointed (e.g., Chief Digital Officer or Deputy Chief Medical Officer for digital transformation)	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A sustainable digital governance structure is established, with regular reporting, leadership support, and formal integration of digital transformation into the organization's strategic development plan	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.2 Strategic Planning for Digital Development

The organization has developed and is implementing a strategy or action plan for the development of digital technologies and telemedicine.

Please assess the level of strategic planning using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No strategic documents related to digital development are in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Digitalization is mentioned only within the organization's general objectives	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Individual digital initiatives exist without a coherent or systematic plan	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	A digital development plan for a 1–3 year period has been formally approved	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Digital transformation is integrated into the organization's overall strategy and departmental operational plans	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A long-term digital development program is in place, with annual KPI monitoring and adaptive goal revision based on performance results	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.3 Financing and Resource Allocation

The organization provides financial support for digital projects and allocates resources for the development of telemedicine services.

Please assess the level of financial and resource support using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No dedicated funding for digital or telemedicine initiatives is available	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Funding is allocated on an ad hoc basis	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Budgeting is conducted through individual project-based requests	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	An annual funding plan for digital initiatives has been defined	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Digital transformation is incorporated into the organization's financial strategy	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A stable digital project budgeting system is in place, supported by internal and external co-financing and aligned with digital strategy priorities	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.4 Coordination and Partnerships

The organization collaborates with external partners (including universities, IT companies, and governmental programs) in the field of digital health and telemedicine.

Please assess the level of collaboration using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No partnerships are in place	<input type="checkbox"/>

1	Memoranda of understanding have been signed without practical implementation	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Individual joint initiatives are implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	The organization participates in governmental digital programs or projects	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Systematic collaboration with partners and universities is established	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	The organization is an active participant in national and international digital programs and initiates and coordinates partnership projects	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.5 Executive Oversight and Leadership Engagement in Digital Transformation

The organization's leadership is actively involved in the governance of digital processes and monitors the outcomes of digital transformation initiatives.

Please assess the level of leadership engagement using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No monitoring of digital processes is conducted	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Reports on digital activities are generated irregularly	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Organizational leadership receives digital performance reports only upon request	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Digital performance indicators are regularly discussed during management meetings	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	An internal monitoring system for digital key performance indicators (KPIs) is implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Leadership is actively engaged in digital training and strategic decision-making, and the results of digital projects are systematically used for managerial adjustments and planning the further development of telemedicine	<input type="checkbox"/>

7. Integration with Medical Information Systems (MIS)

7.1 Integration of Telemedicine Solutions with Core Medical Information Systems

The organization has implemented integration of telemedicine solutions with core medical information systems (e.g., EMIAS, DamuMed, electronic medical records, and regional platforms), enabling bidirectional data exchange.

Please assess the level of integration using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No integration with medical information systems is in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Data are transferred manually	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Partial integration with a single system (e.g., DamuMed)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Automated data exchange is implemented between telemedicine solutions and multiple information systems	<input type="checkbox"/>

4	Full bidirectional integration is achieved with one or more core medical information systems (e.g., EMIAS, DamuMed, electronic medical records)	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	End-to-end integration is implemented at the level of the National Telemedicine Network (NTN), providing unified data access and real-time analytics	<input type="checkbox"/>

7.2 Automation of Telemedicine Service Recording and Analytics

The organization has automated processes for recording, storing, and analyzing data on telemedicine consultations using medical information systems (MIS) and analytical tools. The assessment includes the ability to generate reports, alerts, and analytical dashboards, as well as the use of artificial intelligence (AI) for analyzing the effectiveness of telemedicine services.

Please assess the level of automation using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Telemedicine service recording is performed manually	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Only individual cases are recorded, without systematic data aggregation	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Partial automation is implemented, without the ability to generate analytical reports	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Systematic recording of telemedicine consultations and automated report generation within the MIS are implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Analytical dashboards and automated notifications for physicians and patients are implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Full automation of recording and analytics is achieved using advanced analytical tools, automated notifications, and systematic use of analytical results for managerial decision-making and quality assessment of telemedicine services	<input type="checkbox"/>

7.3 Use of Artificial Intelligence and Intelligent Modules within Medical Information Systems

The organization has implemented artificial intelligence (AI) technologies embedded directly within medical information systems (MIS/CDSS) and used as part of clinical and administrative workflows, rather than as standalone external solutions. These technologies are applied for image analysis, data classification, automated triage, outcome prediction, and clinical decision support.

The maturity level is determined by the degree of AI integration into operational workflows and its role in analytics, monitoring, and improving the clinical and organizational effectiveness of telemedicine services.

Please assess the level of implementation using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
-------	-------------------------------	-------

0	No AI modules are implemented within the medical information systems	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Pilot AI solutions are being tested without clinical application	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	AI is applied only in selected modules (e.g., image recognition or text analysis)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	AI is integrated into operational workflows (e.g., data analysis, triage, automated data validation)	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Comprehensive AI-based support is provided for clinicians and administrators, including performance analytics, recommendations, and automated reporting	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	An intelligent clinical decision support system (CDSS) is implemented, continuously learning from organizational data and adapting to local clinical workflows and patient population characteristics	<input type="checkbox"/>

7.4 Interoperability and Data Exchange Standards

The organization ensures interoperability of medical information systems (MIS) with external platforms based on international and national health data exchange standards, including HL7, FHIR, DICOM, SNOMED CT, as well as formats applied in the Republic of Kazakhstan (e.g., National Telemedicine Network, EMIAS, and others).

This indicator reflects the system's capacity for secure, structured, and standardized exchange of medical information across organizations and information systems.

Please assess the level of interoperability using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	No interoperability with external systems is in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	An internal, non-standardized data format is used	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Data exchange with external systems is limited and requires manual processing	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Selected interoperability standards (e.g., HL7 or FHIR) are partially supported	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Application programming interfaces (APIs) are implemented, and HL7/FHIR/SNOMED standards are used in core data exchange processes	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Full interoperability and interaction with national and international eHealth systems are achieved, including secure automated synchronization and real-time data exchange	<input type="checkbox"/>

7.5 Internal and Mobile Integration

The organization ensures integration of medical information systems (MIS) across internal departments and provides secure mobile access to medical data for healthcare professionals and patients.

This indicator reflects the effectiveness of internal data exchange, the availability of mobile applications or patient/staff portals, as well as the level of data protection and synchronization when accessed via mobile devices.

Please assess the level of integration using a scale from 0 to 5:

Level	Description of Maturity Level	Score
0	Departments operate in isolation, with no data exchange in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Partial data exchange between departments is implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Integration is implemented only for selected departments or services	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	The organization is connected through a unified medical information system (MIS) with centralized data access	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Secure mobile access for healthcare professionals and patients is available through mobile applications or web portals	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	A unified digital ecosystem is operational, providing full internal and external mobile integration, secure access, and real-time data synchronization, including mechanisms for secure data synchronization during temporary loss of connectivity	<input type="checkbox"/>

Abbreviations and Definitions

MIS — Medical Information System

NTN — National Telemedicine Network

EMIAS — Unified Medical Information and Analytical System

mHealth — Mobile Health

AI — Artificial Intelligence

KPI — Key Performance Indicators

CDSS — Clinical Decision Support System

HL7 — Health Level Seven, an international standard for the exchange of health information

FHIR — Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources, a standard for structured health data exchange developed by HL7

DICOM — Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine, a standard for the transmission and storage of medical images

SNOMED CT — Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms, an international clinical terminology system

VPN — Virtual Private Network, a secure virtual data transmission network

SSL — Secure Sockets Layer, a protocol for secure data transmission

ISO — International Organization for Standardization

GOST — State Standard of the Republic of Kazakhstan

API — Application Programming Interface

REST — Representational State Transfer, an architectural style for web services

JSON — JavaScript Object Notation, a structured data format

XML — Extensible Markup Language, a markup language for structured data representation